

1 **Circulating tumor cells in the periphery undergo epithelial-mesenchymal transition.**

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6 We previously described transcriptional qualities of the circulating tumor cell in humans with stage IV
7 metastatic breast cancer, which featured cardinal changes in expression of genes important for
8 establishment of cell polarity, as well as induction of genes functioning in the epithelial mesenchymal
9 transition, including vimentin and zyxin. We report here biologically significant changes in membrane and
10 junctional composition in the circulating tumor cell during metastasis and migration of solid tumor cells in
11 the periphery (blood), including induction of *PSD3*, *JAM2*, laminin *LAMA1* and *HS3ST1*, adhesion
12 molecule *DSCAM*, gap junction molecules *GJA1* and *GJA3*, and *UNC45B*. Axonal guidance genes *SLIT3*,
13 *ROBO3*, ephrin *EPHB6* and semaphorin 4F (*SEMA4F*) were among the genes whose expression was
14 activated at highest quantities during circulation in the periphery concomitant with EMT. Importantly,
15 components of the focal adhesion kinase (FAK) complex, including components talin *TLN2* and *PAK5*
16 which translates inputs at the membrane with changes in cell structure and morphology was coordinately
17 induced during migration in the periphery concurrent with the epithelial mesenchymal transition. During
18 disease progression in humans with breast cancer when cells of the tumor change shape and enter the
19 periphery, activation of genes that function in axonal guidance as well as key changes in junctional
20 composition occur together with induction of the focal adhesion complex, each of which transpire in
21 parallel with the EMT program.
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Results

We measured total transcription in the circulating tumor cell in humans with stage IV breast cancer and used the transcriptome of normal peripheral human blood as a reference to determine genes whose expression was most abundantly activated and repressed in the circulating tumor cell (CTC) in human cancer.

Among the most prominent changes in the CTC was changes in expression of laminin and heparan sulfate molecules LAMA1 and HS3ST1, pleckstrin and sec7 domain-containing *PSD3* and junctional adhesion molecule *JAM2*.

Figure 1: Induction of molecules with functions at the plasma membrane: *PSD3*, *JAM2*, laminin *LAMA1* and *HS3ST1*.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
23362	1.01E-09	0.55	-6.1081186	-3.3593587	255	PSD3	388/	
58494	1.17E-05	0.611	-4.3831179	-2.6801635	52.95	JAM2	2601/	
284217	8.95E-09	0.76	-5.7494505	-4.3667603	166.54	LAMA1	617/	
9957	8.65E-04	0.552	-3.331091	-1.8386224	47.15	HS3ST1	5813/ 21908	

Junctions at the membrane including tight junctions, to which *JAM2* is localized; gap junctions, desmosomes, and adherens junctions. We observed gap junction transcriptional induction in the human CTC.

Figure 2: Induction of gap junction molecules *GJA1* and *GJA3* in the circulating tumor cell.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2697	1.12E-05	0.921	-4.3923912	-4.0445117	49.93	GJA1	2576/	
2700	8.29E-07	0.748	-4.928296	-3.6880072	33.93	GJA3	1558/	

Figure 3: Axonal guidance genes are activated in the circulating tumor cell concomitant with EMT.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
6586	2.77E-11	0.852	-6.6582451	-5.670636	742.57	SLIT3	193/	
64221	2.75E-11	0.81	-6.6596238	-5.3949859	540.75	ROBO3	194/	
2051	2.98E-08	0.676	-5.5427745	-3.7478769	157.9	EPHB6	791/	
10505	1.68E-10	0.573	-6.3884007	-3.663127	163.33	SEMA4F	282/	

Figure 4: Components of the focal adhesion complex are activated during migration to the periphery.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
83660	1.27E-07	0.582	-5.2832762	-3.0751765	201.77	TLN2	1087/	
57144	2.58E-07	0.802	-5.1519133	-4.1313967	72.35	PAK5	1243/	

EMT is characterized by changes in expression of vimentin, TWIST, SNAIL family transcriptional proteins (including *ZEB1* and *ZEB2*), N- and E-cadherin (*CDH2* and *CDH1*, respectively), as well as changes including induction of collagen I and fibronectin. We previously demonstrated activation of vimentin and “non-classical” cadherin *CDH18* in the circulating tumor cell in human breast cancer.

Figure 5: The epithelial-mesenchymal transition gene expression program is actively modulated during migration to the periphery.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
333929	3.34E-04	0.606	3.5874486	2.1724568	8.33	<i>SNAI3</i>	4914/	
220930	9.52E-06	0.504	4.4277459	2.2314102	8.25	<i>ZEB1-AS1</i>	2492/	
1278	1.02E-04	0.828	-3.8851164	-3.2173416	93.43	<i>COL1A2</i>		
60437	8.20E-07	0.673	-4.9306431	-3.3160527	161.16	<i>CDH26</i>	1555/	

Cadherin 26 and the alpha 2 chain of collagen I were transcriptionally activated in the CTC, while *SNAI3* and an antisense RNA of the *ZEB1* locus was repressed.

Together with our previous description of vimentin activation in the human CTC, we demonstrate activation of axon guidance family genes and of the FAK complex, in addition to alterations of tight and gap junctional composition concomitant with EMT in the circulating tumor cell in humans during metastasis.

Discussion

Further study is required to fully understand focal adhesion complex functions and interaction partners during cytoskeletal dynamics associated with EMT and migration to the periphery during metastasis in solid tumor models and in humans with malignancy of the solid tissues (cancer).

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